

Operators Induced By Fuzzy Grill And Fuzzy δ - Sets

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Abstract

In the present paper, we introduce fuzzy grill delta space. Further the operators induced by fuzzy grill and fuzzy delta sets are defined and studied. A new fuzzy topology is obtained with the help of non- fuzzy topological space (fuzzy grill delta space) and the basic properties of the induced topology are studied.

Key words Fuzzy grill, $\phi_{\mathbf{G}}$ - operator, $\psi_{\mathbf{G}}$ – operator, δ – Sets

1. Introduction

The concept of Grill was introduced by Choquet[1] in 1947 since then it has been extensively used by many authors, grill has subsequently turned out to be a very convenient tool for various topological investigations. It is also seen from the literature that in many situations, grill are more effective than certain similar concepts like nets and filters. Chang [2] introduced the notion of fuzzy topology in 1968. In fuzzy setting, the concept of fuzzy grills on fuzzy topological spaces was initiated by Azad [3]. Subsequently Srivastava and Gupta [4] investigated fuzzy basic proximity by use of fuzzy grill. In 2007, the concept of complete ξ grill, a concept similar to that of a bunch in the classical theory and an L -merotopy has been introduced by Mona Khare and Rashmi Singh [5]. They also studied guilds, a concept similar to grill [6]. In 2005, Bhattacharya, Mukherjee and Sinha studied fuzzy compactness via fuzzy grill. Roy and Mukherjee [7] introduced an operator defined by grill on topological spaces. They [8] introduced the operators by fuzzy grill on fuzzy topological showed that it satisfy Kuratowski's closure axioms. In 2010, Das and Mukherjee introduced a kind of generalized fuzzy closed sets in terms of fuzzy grill and discussed their basic properties. Operators on grill m -space is studied by Modak[9].

In the present paper, we have introduced fuzzy grill delta space. We obtained a fuzzy-topology, however fuzzy grill delta space need not be a fuzzy topological space. Here we have studied certain basic properties of this new induced fuzzy

topology. In section 3, two fuzzy operators $\phi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}$ and $\psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}$ induced by fuzzy grill $\mathbf{G}$ and fuzzy delta sets on a fuzzy grill delta space, are introduced. The concept of δ -sets are introduced and discussed in details in [10,11]. A new fuzzy topology $\tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$ is obtained with the help of non-fuzzy topological space and the basic properties of the induced topology are studied.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, by I^X , we mean a topological space (I^X, τ) with no separation properties assumed. If $A \in I^X$, we will adopt the usual notations $Int(A)$ and $cl(A)$ respectively for the interior and closure of A in (I^X, τ) . The power set of I^X is denoted by $P(I^X)$.

Definition 2.1[1]:- A sub collection $\mathbf{G}$ on I^X is called fuzzy grill on X if $\mathbf{G}$ satisfies following conditions

1. $0_X \notin \mathbf{G}$
2. $A \in \mathbf{G}, A \leq B \Rightarrow B \in \mathbf{G}$ where $B \in I^X$
3. $A, B \in I^X$ and $A \vee B \in \mathbf{G} \Rightarrow A \in \mathbf{G}$ or $B \in \mathbf{G}$.

Definition 2.2[4]:- For any two fuzzy sets A and B in an fts X , we define $A + B$ and $A - B$ to be the fuzzy sets given by

$$(A + B)(X) = \begin{cases} A(x) + B(x); & \text{if } A(x) + B(x) \leq 1 \\ 1 & ; \text{if } A(x) + B(x) > 1 \end{cases}$$

And

$$(A - B)(X) = \begin{cases} A(x) - B(x); & \text{if } A(x) > B(x) \\ 0 & ; \text{if } A(x) \leq B(x) \end{cases}$$

$$(A * B)(X) = \begin{cases} A(x) + B(x) - 1; & \text{if } A(x) + B(x) > 1 \\ 0 & ; \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The fuzzy sets on X taking on respectively the constant values 0 and 1 are denoted by 0_X and 1_X respectively. For $A, B \in I^X$, $A \leq B$ if $A(x) \leq B(x)$ for each $x \in X$. AqB notation means that A is quasi-coincident with B i.e. AqB implies $A(x) + B(x) > 1$ for some $x \in X$. The negations of these statements are denoted by $A\bar{q}B$. A fuzzy singleton or a fuzzy point with support X and value α ($0 < \alpha \leq 1$) is denoted by x_α . A is called q - nb d of B or BqA for some fuzzy open set U in X with $U \leq A$, if A itself is fuzzy open then it is called an open- q - nb d of B . The collection of all open q - nb d's of any fuzzy point x_α is denoted by $Q(x_\alpha)$. A subfamily β of the fuzzy topology τ of an fts (X, τ) is a base for τ iff for each fuzzy singleton x_α in (X, τ) and for each open q - nb d U of x_α , $x_\alpha qB$ for some $B \in \beta$ with $B \leq U$. A fuzzy point x_α is called an *adherence point* of fuzzy set A if every open q - nb d of x_α is quasi-coincident with A and $cl(A)$ is the union of all adherence points of A . $M(A)$ is set of molecules of I^X in A . Here, $VM(\downarrow A) = A$, for $A \in I^X$ where $\downarrow A = \{b \in P: \exists a \in A, t. b \leq a\}$ where P is a Poset.

Definition 2.3:- Let (I^X, τ) be an fts and $\mathbf{G}$ be a fuzzy grill on I^X . We define the operator $\emptyset : I^X \rightarrow I^X$, denoted by $\emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A)$ to be the union of all fuzzy points x_α of X such that if $U \in Q(x_\alpha)$ then $A * U \in \mathbf{G}$, where A is a fuzzy set on X and called the fuzzy operator associated with the fuzzy grill $\mathbf{G}$ and the fuzzy topology τ .

Proposition 2.4 [4]:- Let (I^X, τ) be an fts.

- (i) If $\mathbf{G}$ is any fuzzy grill on I^X , then for any two fuzzy sets A and B in I^X , $A \leq B \Rightarrow \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(B)$.
- (ii) If $\mathbf{G}_1$ and $\mathbf{G}_2$ are two fuzzy grills on I^X with $\mathbf{G}_1 \subseteq \mathbf{G}_2$, then $\emptyset_{\mathbf{G}_1}(A) \leq \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}_2}(A)$, for any fuzzy set A in I^X .
- (iii) For any fuzzy grill $\mathbf{G}$ on I^X and any fuzzy set A in I^X , if $A \notin \mathbf{G}$ then $\emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A) = 0_X \notin \mathbf{G}$.
- (iv) $\emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A \vee B) = \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A) \vee \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(B)$
- (v) $\emptyset(\emptyset(A)) \leq \emptyset(A) = cl(\emptyset(A)) \leq cl(A)$
- (iii) $\emptyset(A \vee G) = \emptyset(A)$, for every $G \notin \mathbf{G}$.

Definition 2.5 [4]:- Let $\mathbf{G}$ be a fuzzy grill on an fts I^X . Let us define a map $\psi : I^X \rightarrow I^X$ by $\psi(A) = A \vee \emptyset(A)$ for all fuzzy set A in I^X .

Result 2.5.1 [4]:- The above defined operator ψ is a Kuratowski closure operator.

Definition 2.6 [4]:- In an fts (I^X, τ) , corresponding to a fuzzy grill $\mathbf{G}$ there exists a unique fuzzy topology $\tau^{\mathbf{G}}$ (say) on X given by $\tau^{\mathbf{G}} = \{U \in I^X / \psi(1_X - U) = 1_X - U\}$, where for any $A \in I^X$, $\psi(A) = A \vee \emptyset(A) = \tau^{\mathbf{G}} - cl(A)$.

Theorem 2.7 [4] :- In an fts (I^X, τ)

- (i) If $\mathbf{G}_1$ and $\mathbf{G}_2$ be two fuzzy grills with $\mathbf{G}_1 \subseteq \mathbf{G}_2$, then $\tau^{\mathbf{G}_2} \subseteq \tau^{\mathbf{G}_1}$.
- (ii) If $\mathbf{G}$ be a fuzzy grill and $B \notin \mathbf{G}$, then B is closed in $(I^X, \tau^{\mathbf{G}})$.
- (iii) For any fuzzy set A and any fuzzy grill $\mathbf{G}$ on I^X , $\emptyset(A)$ is $\tau^{\mathbf{G}}$ -closed.

3. Fuzzy grill delta space

Definition 3.1 :- A fuzzy set A is called to be fuzzy δ – set (delta set) if $int(cl(A)) \leq cl(int A)$. Let us denote the collection of fuzzy δ – set (delta set) by τ^δ .

In fuzzy topological space (I^X, τ) , τ^δ is the collection of all the fuzzy δ - sets A . Here int and cl denote interior and closure w.r.t. fuzzy topology τ . Moreover, finite join of δ - set is again a δ – set as $\tau \subseteq \tau^\delta$, then meet of an fuzzy open set with fuzzy δ – set is a fuzzy δ – set. Also the compliment of fuzzy δ – set is a fuzzy δ – set. But this collection does not form a fuzzy topology because arbitrary join of fuzzy δ – set may not be a fuzzy δ – set.

Definition 3.2 :- The space $(I^X, \tau^\delta, \mathbf{G})$ is called fuzzy grill delta space induced by fuzzy grill and collection fuzzy delta sets.

Definition 3.3 :- Let $(I^X, \tau^\delta, \mathbf{G})$ be a fuzzy grill delta space . We define a mapping $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}} : I^X \rightarrow I^X$ denoted by $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) = \vee\{x_\alpha \in I^X : U^*A \in \mathbf{G} \text{ for all } U \in Q_\delta(x_\alpha)\}$, where $A \in I^X$ is called the operator associated with fuzzy grill $\mathbf{G}$ and τ^δ .

Theorem 3.4 :- (I^X, τ^δ) be fuzzy delta space and $\mathbf{G}$ and $\mathbf{H}$ be fuzzy grills on X . For $\in I^X$, the following statement holds

- (i) if $\mathbf{G} \subseteq \mathbf{H} \Rightarrow \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{H}}(A)$
- (ii) if $\emptyset_{\delta(\mathbf{G} \cup \mathbf{H})}(A) = \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{H}}(A)$

Proof(i):- Let $x_\alpha \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)$ implies $U^*A \in \mathbf{G}$, for all $U \in Q_\delta(x_\alpha)$. Since $\mathbf{G} \subseteq \mathbf{H}$, $U^*A \in \mathbf{G}$, for all $U \in Q_\delta(x_\alpha)$. So $x_\alpha \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{H}}(A)$.

(ii) From 3.4 (i), $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)$, $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{H}}(A) \leq \emptyset_{\delta(\mathbf{G} \cup \mathbf{H})}(A)$, this implies $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{H}}(A) \leq \emptyset_{\delta(\mathbf{G} \cup \mathbf{H})}(A)$. For proving $\emptyset_{\delta(\mathbf{G} \cup \mathbf{H})}(A) \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{H}}(A)$, let $x_\alpha \leq \emptyset_{\delta(\mathbf{G} \cup \mathbf{H})}(A)$. This gives $U^*A \in \mathbf{G} \cup \mathbf{H}$, for all $U \in Q_\delta(x_\alpha)$. Hence $U^*A \in \mathbf{G}$ or $U^*A \in \mathbf{H}$. This shows $x_\alpha \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)$ or $x_\alpha \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{H}}(A)$ or $x_\alpha \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{H}}(A)$.

Theorem 3.5 :- Let $(I^X, \tau^\delta, \mathbf{G})$ be a fuzzy grill delta space. Then, for any $A, B \in I^X$, the following is satisfied

- (i) if $A \leq B$, then $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(B)$
- (ii) $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A \vee B) = \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(B)$
- (iii) $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A \wedge B) \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \wedge \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(B)$
- (iv) $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A)$
- (v) if $A \notin \mathbf{G}$ then $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) = 0_X$
- (vi) $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A \vee B) = \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)$

Proof (i):- For $x_\alpha \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)$ implies $U^*A \in \mathbf{G}$, for all $U \in Q_\delta(x_\alpha)$. Since $A \leq B$ implies $U^*A \leq U^*B \in \mathbf{G}$, for all $U \in Q_\delta(x_\alpha)$ implies $x_\alpha \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(B)$.

(ii) From 3.5 (i) $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)$, $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(B) \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A \vee B) \Rightarrow \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(B) \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A \vee B)$. For proving $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A \vee B) \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(B)$, take $x_\alpha \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A \vee B) \Rightarrow U^*(A \vee B) \in \mathbf{G}$, for all $U \in Q_\delta(x_\alpha)$. This implies $U^*A \in \mathbf{G}$ or $U^*B \in \mathbf{G}$, for all $U \in Q_\delta(x_\alpha) \Rightarrow x_\alpha \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(B)$.

(iii) Obvious from 3.5(i)

(iv) $x_\alpha \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)$ implies $U^*A \in \mathbf{G}$, for all $U \in Q_\delta(x_\alpha) \Rightarrow U^*A \in \mathbf{G}$, for all $U \in Q(x_\alpha)$. So $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A)$

(v) $x_\alpha \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)$ implies $U^*A \in \mathbf{G}$, for all $U \in Q_\delta(x_\alpha)$ but $U \leq 1_X \Rightarrow U^*A \leq A \in \mathbf{G}$. So contradiction.

Lemma 3.6:- Let $(I^X, \tau^\delta, \mathbf{G})$ be a fuzzy grill delta space A be the δ – set then, $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq A$.

Theorem 3.6 :- Let $(I^X, \tau^\delta, \mathbf{G})$ be a fuzzy grill delta space. Then, for $A \in I^X$,

- (i) $\emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) \leq \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A)$
- (ii) $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(\emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A)) \leq \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A)$
- (iii) $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) \leq \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A)$

$$(iv) \quad \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}} (\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)$$

Proof :-(i) If $A \leq B$, From 3.5(i) $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(B)$ and from 3.6 Lemma $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq A$. This implies $\emptyset_{\mathbf{G}} (\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) \leq \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A)$.

$$(ii) \quad \text{From Lemma 3.6, } \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(\emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A)) \leq \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A)$$

$$(iii) \quad \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}} (\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A) \text{ (From 3.5 (iv)).}$$

$$(iv) \quad \text{Since } \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq A \Rightarrow \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}} (\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A).$$

Theorem 3.7 :- Let τ_1^δ and τ_2^δ be two collections of all δ – sets on I^X generated by τ_1 , τ_2 respectively and $\tau_1^\delta \subseteq \tau_2^\delta$. Then for any fuzzy grill $\mathbf{G}$ on I^X and fuzzy set A , $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}} (A, \tau_2^\delta) \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}} (A, \tau_1^\delta)$.

Proof:-Let $x_\alpha \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A, \tau_2^\delta)$. Then $U^*A \in \mathbf{G}$, for all $U \in Q_{\tau_2^\delta}(x_\alpha)$. But $\tau_1^\delta \subseteq \tau_2^\delta$, this gives, $U^*A \in \mathbf{G}$, for all $U \in Q_{\tau_1^\delta}(x_\alpha) \Rightarrow x_\alpha \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A, \tau_1^\delta)$.

Definition 3.8:- For a fuzzy grill delta space $(I^X, \tau^\delta, \mathbf{G})$, we define $\psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}} : I^X \rightarrow I^X$ by $\psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) = A \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)$ for all fuzzy set A in I^X . The function $\psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}$ is a Kuratowski closure operator for all fuzzy δ – sets A .

Proof:-(i) $\psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(0_X) = 0_X \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(0_X) = 0_X$

(ii) by definition, $A \leq \psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)$ for $A \in I^X$

$$(iii) \quad \psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A \vee B) = (A \vee B) \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A \vee B) = A \vee B \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(B) = \psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \vee \psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(B).$$

$$(iv) \quad \text{Let } A \text{ be the } \delta \text{ – set. } \psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(\psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) = \psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) = (A \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) = A \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) = A \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)$$

Theorem 3.9:- Let $(I^X, \tau^\delta, \mathbf{G})$ be a fuzzy grill delta space. For all $A \in I^X$,

$$(i) \quad \psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(\psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) \leq \psi_{\mathbf{G}}(A), \text{ where } A \text{ is a } \delta \text{ – set.}$$

$$(ii) \quad \psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq \psi_{\mathbf{G}}(A)$$

Proof:-(i) Since $\psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(\psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) = \psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) = (A \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) = (A \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) \leq (A \vee \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A))$ and hence it follows

$$(ii) \quad \psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) = (A \vee \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A)) \leq (A \vee \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A)) = \psi_{\mathbf{G}}(A).$$

Definition 3.10:-For a fuzzy grill delta space $(I^X, \tau^\delta, \mathbf{G})$, there exist a unique fuzzy topology $\tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$ on I^X given by $\tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}} = \{A \in I^X : \psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(1_X - A) = (1_X - A)\}$ where $A \in I^X$ and $\psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) = \tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}} - cl(A)$. Moreover, $\psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq \tau^\delta - cl(A)$.

Theorem 3.11:- For a fuzzy grill delta space $(I^X, \tau^\delta, \mathbf{G})$, then $\tau^{\mathbf{G}} \subseteq \tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$ and $\tau^\delta \subseteq \tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$.

Proof:-Let A be $\tau^{\mathbf{G}}$ - closed, then $A = \psi_{\mathbf{G}}(A) = (A \vee \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A)) \Rightarrow \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq A$. From 3.5(iv), $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq \emptyset_{\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq A$. Hence $\psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) = A$ and so A is $\tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$ - closed. This implies $\tau^{\mathbf{G}} \subseteq \tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$. If A is a δ – set then $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq A$. This implies A is $\tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$ -closed and

hence $\tau^\delta \subseteq \tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$.

Corollary 3.11.1:- Let $(I^X, \tau^\delta, \mathbf{G})$ be a fuzzy grill delta space. For all $A \in I^X$,

(i) if A is a fuzzy delta set then A is $\tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$ - closed set.

(ii) if $A \notin \mathbf{G}$, then A is $\tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$ - closed set.

Theorem 3.12:- Let τ_1^δ and τ_2^δ be two collections of all δ – sets on I^X generated by τ_1 , τ_2 respectively and $\tau_1^\delta \subseteq \tau_2^\delta$. Then for any fuzzy grill $\mathbf{G}$ on I^X and fuzzy set A , $\tau_1^{\delta\mathbf{G}} \subseteq \tau_2^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$.

Proof:- Since $\tau_1^\delta \subseteq \tau_2^\delta$, $\psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A, \tau_2^\delta) \leq \psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A, \tau_1^\delta) \Rightarrow \tau_1^{\delta\mathbf{G}} \subseteq \tau_2^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$.

Theorem 3.13:- (I^X, τ^δ) be fuzzy delta space and $\mathbf{G}$ and $\mathbf{H}$ be two fuzzy grills on X with $\mathbf{G} \subseteq \mathbf{H}$ then $\tau^{\delta\mathbf{H}} \subseteq \tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$.

Proof:- Let A be a $\tau^{\delta\mathbf{H}}$ - Closed. Then, $A = \psi_{\delta\mathbf{H}}(A) \Rightarrow \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{H}}(A) \leq A$. From 3.4 (i), $\emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) \leq \emptyset_{\delta\mathbf{H}}(A) \leq A$. This implies $\psi_{\delta\mathbf{G}}(A) = A \Rightarrow A$ is $\tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$ – closed. This gives $\tau^{\delta\mathbf{H}} \subseteq \tau^{\delta\mathbf{G}}$.

References

- [1] Choquet, G., 1947, “Sur les notions de felters et de grille”, C.R. Acad. Sci. Paris, 224, 171-173.
- [2] Chang, C. L., 1968, “Fuzzy topological space”, J. Math. Anal. Appl. 24, 182-190.
- [3] Azad, K.K., 1981, “Fuzzy grills and a characterization of fuzzy proximity”, J. Math. Anal. Appl., 79, 13-17.
- [4] Srivastava, P., Gupta, R. L., 1983, “Fuzzy proximity structures and fuzzy ultrafilters”, J. Math. Anal. Appl. 94 (2), 297-311.
- [5] Khare, M., Singh, R., 2008, “Complete ξ -grills and (L, n) -merotopies”, Fuzzy Sets and Systems, 159(5), 620–628.
- [6] Khare, M., Singh, R., 2006, “L-guilds and binary L-merotopies”, Novi Sad J. Math., 36(2), 57–64.
- [7] Roy, B. and Mukherjee, M. N., 2007, “on a typical topology induced by grill”, “Sochow J. Math”, 33 (4), 771-786.
- [8] Mukherjee, M. N. and Das, S., 2010, “Fuzzy Grills and induced fuzzy topology”, МАТЕМАТИККИ ВЕСНИК, 62(4), 285-297.
- [9] Modak, S., 2013, Operators on grill m-space, Bol. Soc. Paran. Mat., 31(2)101-107.
- [10] Chattopadhyay, C. and Roy, U.K., 1992, “ δ - sets, irresolvable and resolvable Spaces”, Math. Slovaca, 42 (3), 371 - 378.
- [11] Modak, S., 2011 “Ideal Delta Space”, Int. J. Contemp. Math. Sciences, 6 (45), 2207 – 2214.